

THE CULTURE OF AZERBAIJAN IN THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES: LANGUAGE, SCRIPT, AND RELIGION

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Abstract: *This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the main directions of Azerbaijani culture in the early medieval period: religious beliefs, language, and writing systems. Particular attention is given to the religious and cultural environment of the Caucasian Albanian state during this era. The study examines, on a scholarly basis, the ideological and social transformations that occurred as a result of the spread of Christianity within the territory of Albania, as well as the influence of this process on the region's architectural traditions, craftsmanship and literary culture. The paper also investigates the origin and linguistic characteristics of the Albanian script and its interrelations with other writing systems in the region. The churches and monasteries built across various regions of Caucasian Albania are evaluated as original examples of early Christian architecture. The main objective of the article is to identify the mutual interaction between religious and written culture within the territory of Azerbaijan during the early medieval period. The research is conducted using comparative-historical and analytical methods. As a result, it is concluded that the culture of Azerbaijan in the early Middle Ages was shaped under the influence of complex religious and ethnic processes, while the religious heritage of Caucasian Albania formed the foundation of this cultural development.*

Keywords: *Christianity, Islam, Albanian language, Urnayr, Church*

Introduction

The early medieval period is considered one of the most significant stages in the cultural development of Azerbaijan. During this era, the transformations in the region's political structure, the evolution of religious beliefs, and the formation of writing systems laid the foundation of the nation's cultural identity. Religion, language and writing, as the fundamental pillars of culture, played a decisive role in shaping the spiritual world of society at that time. The polytheistic beliefs, local cults, and the influence of Zoroastrianism that existed prior to the adoption of Islam—as well as the official recognition of Christianity at the state level, followed later by the spread of Islam—left a profound mark on Azerbaijani culture by creating a new ideological environment. At the same time, the development of linguistic and written culture in the early Middle Ages was closely linked to religious and political processes.

The history of Azerbaijan is studied on the basis of various sources, which can be divided into two main categories: archaeological and written sources. Archaeological research demonstrates that our homeland has a history extending back more than one and a half million years. Having successively passed through all the socio-economic stages of human civilization, Azerbaijan has long been one of the centers of world civilization. From this perspective, the country also possesses very ancient traditions of statehood. Among the earliest states established within the territory of Azerbaijan was the Caucasian Albanian state, which existed for more than eleven centuries—from the 4th century BCE to the 7th century CE.

The scarcity of ancient written sources, and, on the other hand, the biased or even falsified interpretation of the few existing ones over the years, have led to a subjective and distorted understanding of the history of Azerbaijan and in particular, of Caucasian Albania. Numerous aspects of the early medieval history of Caucasian Albania remain obscure, disputed, and insufficiently studied.

During the early Middle Ages, religion and religious thought in Albania, as in many other countries, developed as an inseparable part of the political system and political history. For this reason, information and materials concerning political history often overlap with, and are identical to, those concerning religious matters in written sources. The problem of religion and religious views in Albania during the period under study holds great significance and scholarly interest for understanding the early medieval history of the Albanian state.

The emerging feudal aristocracy skillfully utilized progressive religious ideas to consolidate and strengthen its dominance and authority within society and the country. The rise and development of feudal relations in early medieval Albania created favorable conditions for the spread of Christianity throughout the region.

The development and consolidation of feudal production relations in the country, along with the advancement of production tools and the growth of the economy, in turn, contributed to the rise of science, art, and, in general, culture during the early Middle Ages. Cultural life in the country evolved within a highly complex political environment. Although limited in number, the materials derived from early medieval written sources and the remnants of material culture provide at least some insight into the state of science and culture in Albania during this period. Written sources from the early Middle Ages indicate that during the reign of the Albanian king Asuagen, in the early 5th century, a new Albanian alphabet was created, marking the beginning of written culture in Albania.

The discovery of epigraphic and manuscript examples related to written monuments plays a crucial role in tracing the origins and development of Albania's literary and written tradition. This article is structured and systematically analyzed in accordance with its main components, consisting of an introduction, a conclusion, and two principal sections - **Language and Script Factor and The Religious Factor**.

1. The Factor of Language and Script

The early medieval period of Azerbaijan was characterized not only by political and economic transformations but also by innovations in the fundamental pillars of culture: language, religion, and writing. The cultural values that emerged during this period had a profound impact on the spiritual and intellectual life of the subsequent centuries. It was precisely in this stage that the initial foundations of the Azerbaijani people's cultural identity were laid.

Azerbaijan, whose statehood traditions date back to the 9th century BCE, ranks among the regions that attract attention from multiple historical perspectives. The German philosopher Hegel once remarked, "A nation without a state, in fact, has no history." Despite the categorical nature of this statement, there is an element of truth in it: a nation that lacks statehood or has temporarily lost its political independence cannot fully realize its creative potential or develop its cultural achievements.

According to early medieval written sources and the Albanian historian Movses Kaghankatvatsi, Caucasian Albania which existed between the 4th century BCE and the 7th century CE within the territory of present-day Azerbaijan, extended from the Caucasus Mountains in the north to the Aras River in the south, and from Iberia in the west to the Caspian Sea in the east.

As is known, twenty-six tribes and peoples lived in Caucasian Albania, the majority of whom belonged to Turkic origins. Among them were the Albanians, Massagetae, Gargars, Sakas, Udis, Kangars, Chuls, Pechenegs (Oghuz), Cumans, Kergils, Suvars, Bulgars, Huns, Khazars, Dondars, Kaitags, and others, who together constituted the great majority of the population of the country [1, p.12].

A general acquaintance with the phonetic composition of the Albanian (Turkic) language fully confirms the accuracy of the description by Movses Kaghankatvatsi and Movses Khorenatsi, who referred to it as a "language filled with guttural sounds." For example, in this language, the sound "q" in modern Turkic is often pronounced as "x" or sometimes as "ğ": *qırçaq* – *xırçax*, *qayıtmaq* – *xaytmax*, *qar* – *xar*, and so on. Early medieval written sources indicate that during the reign of King Arsvagen, in

the early 5th century, a new Albanian alphabet was created, marking the beginning of written culture in Albania [3, p.24].

The history of the script created in Albania has not been studied comprehensively or in sufficient depth. A number of scholars, such as I. Abuladze, A. G. Shanidze, K. V. Trever, G. M. Klimov, R. Acharyan, A. Kurdyan, A. S. Mnasakanyan, T. M. Mammadov and others, have addressed this issue in their research to some extent. However, most of these researchers, relying on falsified written sources, failed to analyze and interpret the matter accurately [7, p.234].

Some researchers have expressed skepticism regarding the existence of writing in the Albanian language, while others have attempted to deny it altogether. However, early medieval written sources preserve valuable and undisputed information about the language, script, and alphabet of the Caucasian Albanians. One of the earliest sources, Koryun, provides explicit evidence concerning the existence of the Albanian alphabet and written language [13, p.163].

Another early medieval source also confirms this by stating that writing in the Albanian language existed in the Gargar dialect, which was characterized by its abundance of guttural sounds [7, p.245]. According to these early medieval written sources, following the creation of the alphabet and the emergence of writing in Albania, religious books - including the *Gospel* - were translated into the Albanian language. One of these sources writes: "The venerable Bishop Jeremiah, without delay, began translating the divine books; with their help, the people of the land of Albania at once came to know the prophets and apostles and embraced the Gospel." [9, p.45] The early medieval author *Yeghishe* also attested to the existence of the *Gospel* in the Albanian language and to its use by the inhabitants of Albania.

According to a valuable document cited by the early medieval historian *Ghevond*, when Christianity began to spread in Albania, the Holy Book, the *Gospel*- had already been translated into the Albanian language [4, p. 23].

The historian *Ghevond* writes as follows: "That very book, the *Gospel*, exists intact in all languages. I shall mention a few of them: the first is our Greek language, the second the Roman, the third the Badali... and the twelfth is the Albanian language." [9, p .45]

An Albanian historian also provides information on this subject, stating: "These are the nations that possess writing: the Jews, the Romans (whose script is also used by the Byzantines), the Spaniards, the Greeks... and the Albanians." [8, p.24]

Translations into the Albanian language and evidence of writing in Albanian are accurately reflected in five manuscripts preserved in the Matenadaran.

In 1937, this significant and scientifically valuable discovery was made by the Georgian linguist, Doctor of Philology, and specialist in the Armenian language I. V. Abuladze. While working at the Matenadaran in 1937, Abuladze discovered the manuscript of the Albanian alphabet within a 15th-century, codex numbered 7117 [7, p. 255].

Shortly thereafter, two additional manuscripts containing lists of the Albanian alphabet (№ 3124 and № 2013) were examined and identified by T. I. Ter-Grigoryan at the Matenadaran.[15, p.35]

These 15th-century manuscripts were found within a textbook written in Armenian by the priest and monk Thomas Metsopski, prepared for the students of a monastic school. The textbook included some alphabets-Greek, Syriac, Latin, Georgian, Coptic, and so on, alongside them, a 52-letter Albanian alphabet [9, p,333].

The discovered Albanian script drew the attention of the prominent scholar, the late academician A. G. Shanidze. As a distinguished specialist in Caucasian languages, Shanidze carefully examined the Albanian manuscript, compared it with the alphabets of other Caucasian peoples, and was the first to provide its scholarly interpretation. In 1938, he published a valuable study on the Albanian alphabet. [7, p.288]

This valuable discovery also attracted the attention of the academician R. Acharyan, who published an article demonstrating that the script was indeed the Albanian alphabet and rightfully belonged to the Caucasian Albanians. [15, p. 175] The Albanian alphabet found to belong to the Caucasian Albanians could only acquire true scholarly value and significance if supported by convincing documentary or written evidence in the Albanian language itself. In this regard, in 1938, the Georgian academician A. G. Shanidze wrote in his study:

“I have thought, and I still think, that it is impossible for the script of an entire people who played a prominent role in the cultural and political life of the Caucasus during the Middle Ages to have disappeared without a trace. Excavations must provide us with reliable epigraphic material proving the existence of Albanian writing.” [7, p. 289].

These far-sighted words proved prophetic ten years later. The Albanian epigraphic inscriptions were indeed discovered. In 1948, during archaeological excavations conducted under the direction of the prominent and veteran archaeologist S. M. Qazıyev at the Mingachevir settlement on the left bank of the Kura River, the Museum of the History of Azerbaijan of the Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan SSR organized systematic digs at Early Medieval habitation sites Sudaqlan I–III. During these excavations, the archaeologist R. M. Vahidov discovered an epigraphic monument inscribed with letters of the Albanian alphabet. [10, p.235]

Further archaeological excavations at the Mingachevir settlement revealed additional Albanian inscriptions engraved on several quadrangular, truncated, pyramid-shaped ceramic candlesticks (No. 1, 2, 3, and 4). [10, p.256]

Thus, the study and examination of the valuable materials provided by the Early Medieval written sources, the discovery of the Albanian alphabet manuscript in the Matenadaran, as well as the archaeological evidence obtained during excavations in Mingachevir and other sites - including fragments of Albanian inscriptions and related findings - clearly demonstrate that the assumption denying the existence of writing in the Albanian language is unfounded. These findings decisively refute such claims and provide firm proof that the Albanians possessed their own written language and script. Therefore, it can be confidently stated that, like other civilized nations, the Caucasian Albanians were among the peoples who had developed an independent system of writing and alphabet.

2. The Religious Factor

As in other parts of the world, various forms of early religious beliefs and perceptions also existed in Caucasian Albania. Prior to the adoption of Christianity in the Early Middle Ages, the Albanians and other tribes inhabiting Albania worshipped great deities such as the Sun God, Sky God, Moon God, and other celestial beings [2, p.334]

Before the spread of Zoroastrianism and Christianity in Albania, the population of the country widely practiced the veneration of natural forces-fire, earth, the sun, and similar elements [5, p. 126].

According to the accounts of early medieval authors such as Agathangelos, Koryun, and Yeghishe, prior to the adoption of Christianity, part of the population living in Albania were pagans [14, p.175]. Pagan temples existed in Albania, and pagan priests were active within them. Confirming the information provided by these historians, the Albanian historian Movses Kalankatvatsi also wrote in his work that paganism was widespread in Albania [9, p. 24].

The prominent historian Z. I. Yampolski, in his monograph dedicated to the temples and temple farm that once existed on the territory of Albania, based on historical facts, concluded that these temples possessed large agricultural estates of their own. Each temple was headed by a priest, while the main economic affairs were managed by temple servants. Temples played an extremely significant role in the social and political life of Albania [11, p.235].

In the study of the spread of Christianity in Albania, two successive stages can be identified. The first stage, referred to as the “Apostolic Period”, is associated with the names of the Apostles Thaddeus,

Bartholomew, and Thaddeus disciple Yeghishe (in some sources referred to as Eliseus). This period, which lasted until the 4th century, may conditionally be called the Syriac-oriented period. The second stage, or the Hellenic-oriented period, is linked with Gregory the Illuminator and the Albanian ruler Urnayr [2, p. 266].

The earliest written sources indicate that the first dissemination of Christianity in Albania occurred in the 2nd century AD. During this time, Christian missionaries began their efforts to spread the Christian faith among the population of Albania. According to traditional accounts, the individual who preached Christianity in Albania was Yeghishe, a disciple of the Apostle Thaddeus.

The Albanian historian Movses Kalankatvatsi provides the following account of this event in his work: “After this, Yeghishe, upon the recommendation of our Lord’s brother, the first Patriarch of Jerusalem, Saint Jacob (James), was appointed to the East in the name of the Holy Spirit... He began his preaching in Chola, gathering disciples in various places and endeavoring to make them remember the Savior (Jesus). From there, he went with three of his disciples to the province of Utik.” [12, p.89]

When Saint Yeghishe was preaching Christianity in Albania, one of his disciples was killed by the local population and became a martyr. Nevertheless, “the Saint, as the first preacher of the Christian faith, came to Gis, built a church there, and offered a bloodless sacrifice. This place is the origin of all churches and cities of the East, and it is the source from which we, the people of the East, accepted Christianity” [8, p. 25].

In the middle of the first century, the disciple of Thaddeus, one of the apostles of Jesus Christ, named Yelisey (Eliseus) built the Gis temple, known as the - “Mother of the Churches of the East.” Research has confirmed that this temple corresponds to the Christian church currently located in the village of Kish, in the Sheki district of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Thus, Saint Yeghishe, who lived in the 2nd century AD, is considered one of the holy figures mentioned in historical sources as a preacher of Christianity in Albania.

The Byzantine Empire played a major role in the spread of Christianity within the territory of the Albanian state. In order to strengthen their socio-political position in the Caucasus and promote Christianity, Byzantine emperors frequently sent Christian missionaries to Albania. Therefore, we can observe that the Byzantine Empire served as a strong center for the dissemination of Christianity in Albania. Naturally, there were political motives behind this. The Byzantine Empire, which was often in conflict with the Sasanian Empire, regarded the Albanian state as a strategic ally and made serious efforts to ensure the spread of Christianity there. From this perspective, the Sasanian state which had accepted Zoroastrianism as its official religion, sought to maintain its influence over neighboring states by promoting its own faith and strongly opposing the spread of Christianity.

Despite all these efforts, according to early medieval sources, Christianity was first adopted as the state religion in the early 4th century in the city of Valarshapat, when the Albanian king Urnayr, together with the Albanian feudal lords, nobles, and aristocrats, embraced the new faith. They were baptized and converted to Christianity by Saint Gregory. Following this event, the population of Albania began to accept Christianity through their king, Urnayr.

Urnayr, who was of Arsacid origin, and his successors adopted Christianity not merely out of personal conviction or spiritual devotion, but largely for political reasons. Through the monotheistic religion of Christianity, Urnayr sought to unite the multiethnic Albanian kingdom and to resist the Sasanian Empire, which had embraced Zoroastrianism as its official religion. His successors clearly understood this political strategy and continued to pursue it.

Comprehensive and detailed information about these events is provided by early medieval historians such as Agathangelos, Ayrivanesi, and the Albanian historian Movses Kalankatvatsi.

According to Movses Kalankatvatsi, “After Saint Gregory performed the holy ceremony of the Cross upon those who came from Albania, on the fiftieth day, when they renounced the devil and all his

deeds and professed faith in the Holy Trinity, Urnayr and all his companions entered the holy water.” [9, p. 55] After this, Saint Gregory sent bishops to Albania, Georgia, Abkhazia, and other neighboring regions to teach the doctrines of Christianity and to build churches [12, p. 68].

Following these events, the temples that had been constructed during the period of paganism in Albania were destroyed, and the pagan priests were forced to adopt Christianity.

According to the accounts of early medieval historians, the first head of the Albanian Church was Saint Gregory’s grandson, Grigoris. Movses Khorenatsi provides information about Grigoris’s arrival in Albania as a bishop. The early medieval historian Faustus Buzand also writes about Grigoris: “He was a true preacher of Christianity and impressed everyone with his earnestness and his life of unbearable hardship” [9, p. 45].

Unfortunately, Grigoris was killed by pagans in the plain of Vatnian. After his death, his companions brought his body to Amaras and buried him near the church built by his grandfather, Saint Gregory [9, p. 56]. According to early medieval sources, the burial site of Grigoris’s body was discovered many years later during the reign of King Vachagan III of Albania. By his order, a church was built in Amaras, and a shrine was erected over Grigoris’s grave [9, p. 56]

According to early medieval sources, every year the peoples living in Albania gathered at this site to solemnly commemorate the “heroic day” of Grigoris as a sign of remembrance.

Numerous early medieval sources indicate that churches existed in Albania even before the time of Grigoris. When Grigoris arrived in Albania and began his missionary activity, he had one of the already existing churches restored [7, p. 334]. According to another early medieval account, after Saint Grigoris assumed the rank of Catholicos in Albania, he “...built churches in the cities and villages of the country” [9, p. 39].

The most developed period of Christianity in Albania is associated with the name of the Albanian ruler Vachagan III the Pious. Striving to strengthen the independence of Albania and recognizing the significant political role of an autonomous Albanian Church that could resist foreign religious and political influence as well as assimilation policies, Vachagan considered it essential to reinforce the foundations of the Albanian Church and to strengthen it economically. This could be achieved through the adoption of Albanian ecclesiastical legal norms.

To this end, in 488, Vachagan III convened the Council of Aghuen. The “Aghuen Canons” are of great historical significance, representing the only surviving legal-historical monument of early medieval Albania. This document reflects the social and legal relations of different social strata within the Albanian society of that period.

By the time the Aghuen Canons were adopted, there already existed in Albania both translated and original legal texts that reflected the needs and interests of the Church. Alongside legal norms, these included the translation of the Bible and the canons of the Ecumenical Councils, namely, the Councils of Nicaea (325), Constantinople (381), and Ephesus (431) , whose decrees were binding for all Christians [2, p. 245].

Under the influence of the legal codes of these Ecumenical Councils, as well as due to the internal development of social relations within Albania, the necessity arose to create an independent system of Albanian ecclesiastical laws.

The Statute developed and adopted by the Council of Aghuen consists of a preamble and twenty-one articles. The preamble provides extensive information about the reasons for convening the Council of Aghuen. The analysis of these laws allows them to be divided into four main groups:

1. Laws concerning the clergy, including their mutual relations, rights, and duties;
2. Laws regulating relations between the clergy and secular nobility;
3. Laws governing relations between the clergy and the lay population;
4. Laws of a purely legal nature.

Articles I, II, VI, VII, IX, XV, and XVI belong to the first group. For example, Article I states: “Village priests must show respect to their bishop twice a year, learn from him the ecclesiastical rules based on the Holy Scriptures, and according to custom, bring him a gift once a year.”

Article II stipulates: “When a priest or a person appointed to a lower ecclesiastical rank is ordained, the priest shall pay four dirhams, and for a lower position, two dirhams.” [2, p. 345]

Articles I and II served to strengthen the ecclesiastical hierarchy by defining the duties of lower-ranking clergy toward their superiors and requiring adherence to hierarchical principles during church service.

Articles VI, XV, and XVI were intended to establish the jurisdiction of bishops and priests, members of the higher clergy, over lower-ranking church servants. Priests or deacons who were found guilty of misconduct were judged by their bishop or priest. The forms of punishment included removal from clerical office, confiscation of land holdings, isolation for penance, expulsion from the village, and other disciplinary measures in accordance with the laws.

From a legal perspective, Articles XV and XVI contain elements of both criminal law (regarding defamation) and procedural law (regarding judicial evidence). [2, p. 288]

Articles VII and IX define the proportional relationship between priests and the parishioners belonging to a single church. The number of believers assigned to a church had to correspond appropriately to the number of clergy serving there. The Albanian ecclesiastical hierarchy did not merely adopt these external norms mechanically; rather, it accepted and adapted them to fit the social relations and customary law that existed within Albania itself.

The *Aghuen Canons* regulated the feudal foundations of the new religion and thereby contributed to the further development of feudal relations in Albania. The drafting and supervision of laws concerning Christianity led to the creation of religious unity within the country, which in turn strengthened its political and social cohesion. [6, p. 45]

The spread of Christianity in Caucasian Albania found reflection in its monuments, many of which have preserved their antiquity and uniqueness to the present day. Christian monuments in Albania embody almost all the characteristic features of Eastern Christianity. The history of Albanian Christian monuments can be divided into three main periods:

1. The Early Christian period (1st–3rd centuries)
2. The period when Christianity became the official religion (4th–6th centuries)
3. The Arab domination period (7th–9th centuries)
4. The Renaissance period of Albanian Christian architecture (10th–13th centuries)

During the Early Christian period, the first Christian temple in the Caucasus was built precisely within the territory of Caucasian Albania, which corresponds to the modern Republic of Azerbaijan. Early Christian temples in Albania were often constructed on the sites of ancient sanctuaries and pagan shrines, as well as inside caves [7, p. 344].

The architectural style of these earlier temples was modified: an apse was added on the eastern side, while an entrance was placed on the western side. In this way, ancient sanctuaries were transformed into Christian churches. The earliest Christian churches were of simple construction, generally consisting of a single-nave hall covered with an arched vault. The first Christian monument is known as the *Gis Temple*, about which information has already been provided above.

With the adoption of Christianity, centrally domed and basilican worship structures began to appear in Caucasian Albania. These buildings had reached a mature stage in terms of both architectural planning and structural solutions. The basilica of Gum, as well as the circular temples located in the villages of Boyuk Amili and Lakit, stand as striking examples of this architectural perfection. These monuments are situated close to one another, within the northwestern regions of present-day Azerbaijan, which served as the central area of Caucasian Albania during the early Middle Ages. [2, p. 78]

In the early years of the spread of Christianity, most of the earlier pagan temples were reconstructed and adapted for Christian worship. The rare circular temples found in the regions of Qabala, Qakh, and Zaqatala in Azerbaijan vividly confirm this historical reality.

Monuments belonging to the initial stage of the spread of Christianity clearly demonstrate that the new architectural challenges faced by Albanian builders were not immediately resolved. Abandoning centuries-old architectural traditions proved to be difficult. For this reason, the earliest Christian monuments retained significant similarities with earlier pagan sanctuaries and markedly differed from the churches constructed in the subsequent historical periods of Albania.

The temple of Mithra, dedicated to the deity of warriors and peaceful farmers, located at Kilisadagh near the village of Boyuk Amili in the Gabala region, represents a monument of exceptional architectural sophistication. The structure is a centrally domed, two-tiered composition. The outer surface of the temple's wall is designed in an irregular twelve-sided polygonal form, while the inner surface constitutes a cylindrical space with a diameter of approximately 10.4 meters. A secondary inner circle served as a stylobate for eight columns supporting the structure. The temple was constructed under the influence of certain elements of ancient (classical) architecture [8, p. 78].

Another prominent example of Albanian ecclesiastical architecture is the circular temple in the village of Lakit, located about one kilometer from the modern village in the Qakh region of Azerbaijan. The construction techniques employed in this building allow it to be dated to the 6th century. The Lakit temple is considered one of the earliest prototypes that contributed to the formation of the tetraconch structures characteristic of the South Caucasus.

Numerous other monuments of a similar nature can be cited, structures that originally functioned as early Christian temples and were later transformed into churches, thus reflecting the architectural evolution and the gradual Christianization of sacred space in Caucasian Albania.

The church of the Aghoghlan Monastery, located in the village of Sos in the Khojavend district, is among the largest basilica-type structures in the region. According to a 5th-century author, "the first church here was built in the 330s in honor of Grigoris, the grandson of Gregory the Illuminator." The basilica was constructed on the left bank of the Aghoghlan River, in the so-called "sacred" valley, at the center of the ancient settlement known as Amaras. The monument has undergone multiple reconstructions and restorations over the centuries; nevertheless, its original architectural features have largely been preserved. The basilica is an elongated structure consisting of three naves separated by two pairs of columns.

Archaeological excavations in Gabala have uncovered a bronze censer dated by specialists to the 7th century [2, p. 289]. Clay censers have also been discovered in the territories of Christian sanctuaries in Barda and Orankhala. In addition, numerous candlesticks of various forms were found during excavations of Christian temples and residential sites in Mingachevir. According to archaeologist R. M. Vahidov, these candlesticks were primarily used during worship in churches and Christian sanctuaries, and thus are considered ecclesiastical artifacts.

One of the most significant periods in the development of Albanian architecture coincided with the time when Christianity became the official religion of Caucasian Albania. This era began with the initiatives undertaken by the Albanian ruler Urnayr to promote Christianity as the state religion and continued until the ecclesiastical reforms and church-building activities implemented by King Vachagan III the Pious.

As is well known, King Vachagan III carried out extensive construction projects with the aim of spreading Christianity throughout the country. According to *The History of the Albanians*, he "had as many churches built as there are days in the year."

The monuments located in the territory of Karabakh were preserved by Kipchak tribes during the wars waged between the Khazars and the Arabs for control over Azerbaijan. It should be noted that the Kipchaks were Turkic tribes who had adopted Christianity [3, p. 78].

Various material and spiritual cultural elements associated with the Kipchak Turks can be found in the Albanian Christian monuments. The Albanian–Kipchak architectural sites located around Lake Goycha, in Zangezur, and in Karabakh testify to the rich cultural heritage of the local Turkic tribes.

The etymological explanation of the name *Gandzasar Monastery* as “Temple Mountain” (where *kənisə* means “temple” and *sər* means “hill” or “mountain”) further supports this connection. Likewise, the memorial stones dedicated to Kipchak-origin military leaders found in the Albanian Christian monuments of Khudavang and Gandzasar, along with their engraved depictions, confirm the close association between the Albanian and Kipchak cultural traditions. The fact that the Albanian-Khachen rulers bore the title *tegin* and their wives were called *khatun* is also not coincidental [7, p. 277].

The regions where Albanian–Kipchak Christian architectural monuments have suffered the greatest destruction are primarily located in the western part of Azerbaijan (present-day Armenia), the Borchali district encompassing the eastern part of modern Georgia, and the historical territory of Derbent. In the districts of Karbibasar and Shorayel (Sirak), Kipchak churches had already become widespread from the early medieval period onwards.

Most of the ancient churches located in the Karbibasar district, which lies along the western border of Azerbaijan, were built by Christian clerics of Kipchak origin. Among the principal Christian religious monuments of Karbibasar are the *Church of the Holy Cross* constructed in the 4th century; the *Ashtarak monuments* (located in the village of Ashtarak) dating from the 7th–13th centuries; the *Karmravor Church* built in the 7th century by Kipchak priests named Manas and Grigori; the *Aruj Church* from the 7th century; the 5th-century church in the village of Ovanavang; the *Kazakh Basilica* in the city of Abaran from the 5th century; and the 5th-century church in the village of Ashnak [3, p. 67].

In Zangezur, the Albanian–Kipchak Christian monuments were converted by Armenians into Gregorian churches, while many others were completely destroyed. One of these Christian temples, which remains in ruins as a result of Armenian vandalism, is the *Gyzyl Church* (the Golden Church) temple.

Among the Albanian–Christian monuments of Zangezur, the *Tatev Monastery Complex* occupies a particularly significant place. This monument is situated near the ancient Gorus Fortress, which historically belonged to the local Turkic tribes. According to historical records, the church bell of the complex was stolen in the early 20th century by Andranik, the leader of an Armenian Dashnak band, melted down, and used to manufacture weapons intended for the extermination of the local Turkic–Muslim population.

At present, acts of so-called “spiritual terror” by the Armenian Gregorian Church against the historical monuments of Azerbaijan’s western regions continue. The historical and cultural heritage of the local Turkic–Muslim population is being plundered and subjected to systematic destruction by Armenians.

Thus, the religious culture of Caucasian Albania, particularly with the spread of Christianity, became even more enriched. The churches and monasteries constructed during this period formed an integral part of the country’s cultural heritage. These monuments are not only evidence of religious belief but also serve as vivid expressions of the architectural thought and aesthetic taste of their time.

Conclusion:

The examination of early medieval written sources and the works of researchers indicates that Caucasian Albania bordered Sarmatia to the north, joining it along the northern foothills of the Greater Caucasus Mountains. In the southwest, the territory of Albania extended to the upper reaches of the Araxes River, including the left bank of this river. To the south, its territory stretched to the confluence

of the Araxes and Kura rivers, encompassing Paytakaran and reached as far as the Mughan and Mil plains. To the east, the Albanian state bordered the Caspian Sea, while to the west, it shared borders with the Kingdom of Iberia. The analysis of the aforementioned early medieval written sources, as well as toponymic, linguistic, and anthropological data and scholarly works, demonstrates that in ancient times and the early Middle Ages (3rd-7th centuries), the main component of the population of Caucasian Albania consisted of Turkic-speaking tribes belonging to the Turkic family group.

The study of early medieval written and archaeological sources, along with other materials, reveals that before the spread of Christianity, astral religious beliefs were widespread in Albania. From the 2nd century AD onward, Christianity and its doctrines began to spread in the region. The Christian faith was disseminated and preached in Albania directly by missionaries coming from Jerusalem, the birthplace of Christianity. In the early 4th century, Christianity was officially adopted as the state religion of Caucasian Albania.

However, the spread of Christianity in Albania during the early Middle Ages should be regarded as a progressive step, as it was directed against the pagan forces that hindered the development of new feudal productive forces and relations of production. Christianity contributed to bringing Albania closer politically, economically, and culturally to the advanced Christian countries of the East. The adoption of Christianity as the state religion further strengthened Albania's economic, political, and cultural ties with its neighboring states. The study and analysis of early medieval written sources indicate that during this period, there existed religious books in the Albanian language intended for the preaching and dissemination of Christianity. In the early Middle Ages, sacred religious texts such as the Gospel, the Old Testament (the ancient pre-Christian section of the "Bible"), and the "New Testament", other Christian scriptures, were translated into the Albanian language and were known among the Christian Albanian population. Albanian clergy and Christian missionaries actively used these sacred texts while spreading and promoting the Christian faith throughout the country.

The study and analysis of early medieval written sources vividly demonstrate that from the very foundation of the Albanian Church and the adoption of Christianity as the state religion from the 4th century up to the 7th century-it remained completely independent and was not subordinate to any other Christian church. Consequently, it could not have played any significant role in the creation or development of the Albanian script and alphabet.

Thus, an objective examination and accurate analysis of the valuable materials contained in early medieval written sources clearly indicate that during the early Middle Ages, there existed a rich body of literature in the Albanian language. Contrary to the claims of certain falsifying researchers who deny the existence of literature in the Albanian language, the study of these authentic early medieval materials reveals that following the creation of the new Albanian alphabet, its practical implementation began.

Research also shows that during the early Middle Ages, the interaction between religious beliefs, language, and writing systems constituted one of the key directions shaping the cultural development of Azerbaijan and had a profound influence on the intellectual life of subsequent periods.

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